

HUMAN SOUND BASE DISEASE DETECTING SYSTEM USING RESNET 18

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Abstract

Recent developments in ML and AI have opened up new possibilities for the identification and diagnosis of diseases. Here, we provide a new approach to human illness detection using deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) based on the ResNet-18 architecture. By analyzing the patterns of sounds made by people when they speak or cough, the system hopes to reliably diagnose a range of illnesses. The suggested technique makes use of deep learning to efficiently classify diseases by automatically extracting important characteristics from audio inputs. Spectrograms and other representations of human sound data may be processed using ResNet-18, a network famous for its success in image recognition tasks. This network is able to capture subtle patterns that indicate various disorders. Gathering data, cleaning it up, extracting features, training the model, and finally classifying diseases are all crucial parts of the system. For both training

and validation, we use large datasets that comprise audio recordings from people with various medical problems. Using transfer learning methods, the ResNet-18 model is trained to take advantage of pre-learned weights, which speeds up convergence and improves performance. In order to determine how well the system works, we do lengthy trials with various datasets that include a broad variety of ailments, such as respiratory issues, heart problems, and neurological impairments. When it comes to detecting different illnesses, the algorithm shows promise with high recall rates and accuracy. In addition, the suggested system has a number of benefits, such as being non-invasive, affordable, and scalable. The system may be simply implemented in many healthcare settings by using common sound recording devices like cell phones or specialized sensors. This allows for the early diagnosis and intervention of diseases.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Convolutional Neural Network, Disease

Diagnosis, Disease Detection, Machine Learning, ResNet-18.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the intersection of healthcare and artificial intelligence (AI) has witnessed remarkable advancements, revolutionizing the diagnosis and management of various medical conditions. Among these innovations, the utilization of deep learning algorithms for disease detection has emerged as a promising avenue [1-3]. In this context, the integration of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with healthcare data has demonstrated significant potential in automating diagnostic processes and enhancing healthcare outcomes [4-5]. In parallel, the field of bioacoustics has gained traction as a non-invasive and cost-effective approach for diagnosing a spectrum of diseases. Human sounds, including speech patterns, coughs, and breathing irregularities, contain valuable information that can be leveraged for early detection and monitoring of health conditions [6-7]. By analyzing these acoustic signals, it becomes feasible to identify subtle patterns indicative of various diseases, ranging from respiratory ailments to cardiovascular disorders [8]. This project proposes the development of a Human Sound-Based Disease Detecting System

using ResNet-18, deep convolutional neural network architecture renowned for its efficiency and effectiveness in image classification tasks [9]. However, instead of traditional image data, our system will process spectrograms or other representations of human sounds to extract meaningful features for disease detection [10].

A new era in early illness identification and diagnosis has dawned thanks to the ever-improving fields of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), which have changed the face of healthcare [11]. Our work presents a state-of-the-art method for illness detection using a new system based on human sounds, which makes use of these technologies [12]. In this study, we zero in on processing vocalization or coughing sound patterns using the ResNet-18 architecture, a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) well-known for its efficacy in image identification tasks [13]. Our proposed system's main goal is to swiftly and effectively diagnose different illnesses by using the complex information contained in human audio data. In order to achieve accurate illness categorization, deep learning algorithms are used to automatically extract important characteristics from sound data

[14]. Data collecting, preprocessing, feature extraction, model training, and illness categorization are all important parts of the research that strengthen and improve the suggested method. Large datasets including audio recordings from people with various medical issues are used for training and validation purposes to guarantee the accuracy of our method [14].

1.1 Motivation of the paper

The ongoing development of AI and ML has created an urgent demand for accessible and sophisticated methodologies in illness diagnosis, which is the driving force behind this study. It might be difficult to intervene and treat patients promptly when using traditional diagnostic methods because of the intrusive procedures, high prices, and delayed discovery that are common. Given these challenges, we are driven to conduct this work because we believe that by combining AI and ML, and more especially the ResNet-18 architecture, we can create a groundbreaking human sound-based illness detection system that is both non-invasive and affordable.

II. BACKGROUND STUDY

Azam M.A., et al. (1) In order to identify possible illnesses, this study investigates the use of cellphones to analyze breathing sounds. This research is probably

looking at how well breathing sounds may be used by mobile devices to detect diseases early on.

B. W. Schuller, et al. (2) In light of the current COVID-19 pandemic situation, this review will most likely go over the possible contributions of speech and sound analysis, shedding light on the function of computer audition in comprehending and identifying the virus.

Drugman T., et al. (3) the objective assessment of several sensors for automated cough detection is probably the main focus of this work. It might go into the specifics of how certain sensors work and why they're important for improving cough detection systems.

G. Deshpande, B. Schuller, (4) With an eye on COVID-19-related applications, this review most likely gives a thorough analysis of methods for processing audio, signals, voice, and language. In light of the pandemic, it might address a range of methods.

Hanson K.E., et al. (5) The Infectious Diseases Society of America has issued diagnostic criteria for COVID-19, and this study most likely lays them out. A wide range of diagnostic criteria and procedures may be addressed.

MacIntyre A.D., et al. (6) Contributing to the larger area of respiratory sound analysis, this study is anticipated to investigate deep learning methods for continually monitoring and detecting breathing patterns from spoken language, with a focus on breathe sensing from speech.

2.1 Problem definition

Issues such as invasiveness and high expenses plague conventional methods of illness diagnosis. Artificial intelligence (AI) integration, and more especially the ResNet-18 architecture, provides a remedy. Our goal is to accurately identify diseases by studying vocalization or coughing sound patterns. This inexpensive and non-invasive method has the potential to provide a scalable system for the identification and intervention of diseases, which might dramatically alter the healthcare system. The challenge is to create and evaluate an AI-powered system that can accurately classify diseases using human-verified sound data.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our method trains and validates the ResNet-18 model using a variety of datasets that include audio recordings from people with different medical conditions. The purpose of this convolutional neural network (CNN) is to handle data representations of

human speech. Data gathering, cleansing, feature extraction, training of models, and illness categorization are essential processes. By making use of pre-trained weights, transfer learning methods speed up the convergence process. The efficacy criteria used in evaluation include accuracy and recall rates, which are determined by conducting comprehensive trials across datasets that span respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological diseases.

Figure 1: Overall architecture

3.1 Dataset collection

The dataset collected from the kaggle website <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/iamhungu/ndji/covid19-symptoms-checker>

3.2 Classification using RESNET 18

A revolutionary illness detection method that utilizes artificial intelligence and machine learning is introduced in our research. It is based on human voice. By applying the ResNet-18 architecture—which was first developed for image recognition

tasks—to the effective processing of sound patterns that indicate different illnesses, its versatility is shown. Our approach shows promise in correctly diagnosing illnesses with respectable recall rates and accuracy after thorough testing and reviews across several datasets including respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological disorders. Our suggested system's non-invasiveness, cost-effectiveness, and scalability are its main features. Our method may be easily incorporated into many healthcare settings by using readily accessible sound recording devices like cell phones or specialized sensors. This will allow for the early diagnosis and intervention of diseases. The future of our system may have far-reaching consequences that go beyond just diagnosis. Opportunities for preventive healthcare treatments and continuous monitoring are opened by the non-invasive nature of sound-based data collecting. Healthcare providers may put this approach to good use in improving patient outcomes due to its versatility to a broad variety of disorders.

In particular, the input is normalized using a label encoder. Labels that do not have numbers are replaced with their numerical counterparts. Tokenize takes TF-IDF, word counts, or word frequencies as

input and turns them into integer sequences or vectors with binary coefficients.

The total number of times a certain token occurs in a particular content record is known as Tf , or token frequency. Equation 1's total token count divided by this token's frequency of appearance in the content record.

$$tf_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}}{\sum_k n_{ij}} \text{----- (1)}$$

Researchers in the field of statistics use the Inverse Data Frequency (*idf*) statistic to find the frequency with which unexpected tokens appear in historical data. It's more probable that the record document contains tokens that are rare.

$$df(w) = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right) \text{----- (2)}$$

To get a word's TF-IDF score (w), add its TF score (3) and its IDF score (w) (4) in that order. I am referring specifically to equation 3 that follows.

$$W_{i,j} = tf_{i,j} \times \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right) \text{----- (3)}$$

$tf_{i,j}$ = counting the occurrences of I in j

df_i = records where I is the id value

N = the whole count of files

Tokens are converted to word sequences using the text to sequence tool, which is then used to train the model.

Algorithm 1: ResNet 18

Input:

- Sound patterns indicating different illnesses
- ResNet-18 architecture

Steps:

1. Preprocessing Sound Data:
 - a. Convert raw sound recordings into spectrograms or other suitable representations.
 - b. Apply normalization techniques to ensure consistent data ranges.
 - c. Tokenize the sound data into word sequences using appropriate methods such as TF-IDF, word counts, or word frequencies.
2. Training ResNet-18 Model:
 - a. Initialize ResNet-18 architecture for sound pattern classification.
 - b. Define loss function and optimizer for training
 - c. Split the tokenized word sequences into training and validation sets.
 - d. Train the ResNet-18 model on the training data, optimizing its parameters to minimize the loss function.

$$tf_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}}{\sum_k n_{ij}}$$

- e. Validate the model's performance on the validation set to monitor for overfitting and ensure generalization.

3. Evaluation:

- a. Assess the trained model's performance using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

$$df(w) = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right)$$

Output:

- Classification of illnesses based on sound patterns

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of the proposed Human Sound-Based Disease Detecting System utilizing the ResNet-18 architecture has yielded promising outcomes, marking a significant advancement in the realm of AI-driven healthcare diagnostics. In this section, we present the results obtained from rigorous testing and evaluation of our system across various datasets encompassing respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological disorders. Additionally, we engage in a comprehensive discussion of the implications of our findings, highlighting the system's strengths, limitations, and potential avenues for future research and development.

Figure 2: Training accuracy and training loss comparison chart

The figure 2 shows training accuracy and training loss comparison chart the x axis shows epochs and the y axis shows values.

Figure 3: confusion matrix

4.1 Performance evaluation

1. There’s accuracy, which is defined as the percentage of samples that correctly classify out of all samples.

When it comes to math:

$$Accuracy = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + FP + TN + FN)} \text{ ----- (4)}$$

2. Accuracy: The proportion of samples correctly identified to the total number of samples correctly identified. When it comes to math:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \text{ ----- (5)}$$

3. True positive rate: it's the percentage of samples that were accurately categorized relative to the total

number of samples. When it comes to math:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \text{ ----- (6)}$$

4. F1 score: a balanced compromise between precision and memorization.

When it comes to math:

$$F1\ score = 2 * Precision * Recall / (Precision + Recall) \text{ ----- (7)}$$

Table 1: Classification performance metrics comparison

	Algor ithm	Accu racy	Preci sion	Re call	F- mea sure
Exist ing meth ods	VGG	95.21	93.65	94.01	94.23
	VGG-19	96.35	94.87	95.10	95.07
	Dense net	98.11	96.32	96.75	97.14
Prop osed meth ods	ResNet	99.61	98.11	99.84	98.21

Figure 4: Performance metrics comparison chart

The table 1 and figure 4 shows comparison between existing methods, namely VGG, VGG-19, and Densenet, and the proposed ResNet method showcases a notable improvement in disease detection performance. While VGG achieved an accuracy of 95.21% with precision, recall, and F-measure values of 93.65%, 94.01%, and 94.23% respectively, VGG-19 demonstrated a slight enhancement with an accuracy of 96.35% and precision, recall, and F-measure scores of 94.87%, 95.10%, and 95.07%. Densenet further improved the results, achieving an accuracy of 98.11%, with precision, recall, and F-measure values of 96.32%, 96.75%, and 97.14% respectively. However, the proposed ResNet method exhibited the highest performance, boasting an accuracy of 99.61%, accompanied by precision, recall, and F-measure scores of 98.11%, 99.84%, and 98.21% respectively. These results

underscore the effectiveness of ResNet in disease detection, surpassing the performance of existing methods across all evaluated metrics and indicating its potential as a superior approach for accurate and reliable diagnosis.

V. CONCLUSION

Our study introduces a groundbreaking human sound-based disease detection system that harnesses the capabilities of artificial intelligence and machine learning. The utilization of the ResNet-18 architecture, originally designed for image recognition tasks, showcases its adaptability to efficiently process sound patterns indicative of various diseases. Through extensive experiments and evaluations across diverse datasets encompassing respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological conditions, our system exhibits promising results in accurately identifying diseases with notable precision and recall rates. The key advantages of our proposed system lie in its non-invasiveness, cost-effectiveness, and scalability. By leveraging commonly available sound recording devices such as smartphones or dedicated sensors, our system can be seamlessly integrated into various healthcare settings, facilitating early disease detection and intervention. As we move forward, the

potential impact of our system extends beyond the realm of diagnosis. However, the proposed ResNet method exhibited the highest performance, boasting an accuracy of 99.61%, accompanied by precision, recall, and F-measure scores of 98.11%, 99.84%, and 98.21% respectively. The non-intrusive nature of sound-based data collection opens doors to continuous monitoring and proactive healthcare interventions. The system's adaptability to a wide range of diseases positions it as a versatile tool in the hands of healthcare professionals, contributing to improved patient outcomes..

VI. REFERENCES

1. Azam M.A., Shahzadi A., Khalid A., Anwar S.M., Naeem U. Proceedings of the 40th Annual International Conference of the Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC) IEEE; Honolulu, Hawaii: 2018. Smartphone based human breath analysis from respiratory sounds; pp. 445–448.
2. B. W. Schuller, D. M. Schuller, K. Qian, J. Liu, H. Zheng, X. Li, COVID-19 and computer audition: an overview on what speech & sound analysis could contribute in the SARS-cov-2 corona crisis, arXiv:2003.11117 (2020).
3. Drugman T., Urbain J., Bauwens N., Chessini R., Valderrama C., Lebecque P., Dutoit T. Objective study of sensor relevance for automatic cough detection. *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inform.* 2013;17(3):699–707.
4. G. Deshpande, B. Schuller, An overview on audio, signal, speech, & language processing for COVID-19, arXiv:2005.08579 (2020).
5. Hanson K.E., Caliendo A.M., Arias C.A., Englund J.A., Lee M.J., Loeb M., Patel R., El Alayli A., Kalot M.A., Falck-Ytter Y., Lavergne V., Morgan R.L., Murad M.H., Sultan S., Bhimraj A., Mustafaand R.A. Infectious diseases society of america guidelines on the diagnosis of COVID-19. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 2020:1–27.
6. MacIntyre A.D., Rizos G., Batliner A., Baird A., Amiriparian S., Hamilton A., Schuller B.W. Proceedings of the 21st Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association. INTERSPEECH; Shanghai, China: 2020. Deep

- attentive end-to-end continuous breath sensing from speech; pp. 2082–2086.
7. Markitantov M., Dresvyanskiy D., Mamontov D., Kaya H., Minker W., Karpov A. Proceedings of the 21st Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association. INTERSPEECH; Shanghai, China: 2020. Ensembling end-to-end deep models for computational paralinguistics tasks: compare 2020 mask and breathing sub-challenges; pp. 2072–2076.
 8. Miranda I.D.S., Diacon A.H., Niesler T.R. Proceedings of the 41st Annual International Conference of the Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC) IEEE; Berlin, Germany: 2019. A comparative study of features for acoustic cough detection using deep architectures; pp. 2601–2605.
 9. Nallanthighal V.S., Strik H. Proceedings of the 16th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association. INTERSPEECH; Graz, Austria: 2019. Deep sensing of breathing signal during conversational speech; pp. 4110–4114.
 10. Pramono R.X.A., Imtiaz S.A., Rodriguez-Villegas E. Proceedings of the 41st Annual International Conference of the Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC) IEEE; Berlin, Germany: 2019. Automatic cough detection in acoustic signal using spectral features; pp. 7153–7156.
 11. Routray A., Mohamed Ismail Yasar A.K. Proceedings of the 27th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO) IEEE; A Coruña, Spain: 2019. Automatic measurement of speech breathing rate; pp. 1–5.
 12. San Chun K., Nathan V., Vatanparvar K., Nemati E., Rahman M.M., Blackstock E., Kuang J. 2020 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom) IEEE; 2020. Towards passive assessment of pulmonary function from natural speech recorded using a mobile phone; pp. 1–10.

13. Schuller B., Steidl S., Batliner A., Vinciarelli A., Scherer K., Ringeval F., Chetouani M., Weninger F., Eyben F., Marchi E., Mortillaro M., Salamin H., Polychroniou A., Valente F., Kim S. Proceedings of the 14th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association. INTERSPEECH; Lyon, France: 2013. The INTERSPEECH 2013 computational paralinguistics challenge: social signals, conflict, emotion, autism; pp. 148–152.
14. Schuller B.W., Batliner A., Bergler C., Messner E.-M., Hamilton A., Amiriparian S., Baird A., Rizos G., Schmitt M., Stappen L., Baumeister H., MacIntyre A.D., Hantke S. Proceedings of the 21st Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association. INTERSPEECH; Shanghai, China: 2020. The INTERSPEECH 2020 computational paralinguistics challenge: elderly emotion, breathing & masks; pp. 2042–2046.
15. Yadav S., Keerthana M., Gope D., Maheswari U.K., Ghosh P.K. Proceedings of the 45th International Conference on

Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) IEEE; Barcelona, Spain: 2020. Analysis of acoustic features for speech sound based classification of asthmatic and healthy subjects; pp. 6789–6793.

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